

ADMIXTURE OF USED ENGINE OIL BLENDED WITH KEROSENE AS A SUBSTITUTE FOR INDUSTRIAL FUEL

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ABSTRACT

The admixture of used engine oil blended with kerosene as a substitute for industrial fuel was experimented to determine its viability for use as an industrial fuel in foundry workshop. Various types of industrial fuel exist, some of which include diesel containing 84.4% of carbon, 11.7% of hydrogen, 1.4% of nitrogen and 0.60% of sulphur, a boiling point of about 550⁰F (287.78⁰C), of 250⁰F (121.11⁰C) and its fractionated pouring temperature of 515⁰F(268.33⁰C). Equipment used for the experiment include crucible furnace, fuel tank, inlet pipe, wire gauze, flexible hose, the injector nozzles, the electric motor blower, the delivery hose, the control knob, the mixture chamber, the combustion chamber, and the crucible pots (the excavators). Four liters of the mixture of used engine oil to kerosene at a varying ratio of 2:1, 3:2, 5:3,5:2, 3:1, 4:1, 5:1 and 6:1 was used to carry out the test. Most appropriate result of the experiment was obtained at a combination ratio of 6:1 with four liters of the mixture melting 10kg of zinc in 22 minutes.

KEY WORDS: Melting, mixture, fuel, furnace, combustion

INTRODUCTION

This work was carried out with the desire to reduce the cost of fuel used in our furnaces and burners by making use of used engine oil mixed in a certain proportion with kerosene; the used engine oil taking the higher proportion of the mixture. This will serve as an alternative to diesel, coal, and other hydrocarbons which will be used for firing industrial equipments like boilers and in a foundry workshop.

Industrial fuel is normally sourced from crude oil. Most scientists believed that oil and natural gas were formed millions of years ago, but the only living then were tiny sea plants and sea creatures called plankton. The seas were full of plankton, the water was like thick soup, and the sun's energy helped the plankton to grow. Everything around us is made of chemicals; these chemicals are of two types, carbon and oxygen. When the plankton died oxygen left their bodies. This is only why carbon and hydrogen are in the remains of the tiny plankton that later turned into oil and natural gas.

This natural gas (crude oil) is extracted from the ore in the soil, which is being refined into industrial fuels such as gasoline, diesel oil, kerosene and black oil. (Sauvain,1987).

Aim and objectives

This work is aimed at producing a cost effective industrial fuel as an alternative to the present fuel which is majorly expensive, for use in industrial boilers and foundry workshop. This will help reduce the cost of generating heat in small and medium scale industries and also help reduce environmental pollution by recycling used engine oil instead of throwing it away.

Scope of the work

This work will be limited to using engine oil that has been used by an automobile vehicle after its original lubrication value has been used up and then mixed with kerosene.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Industrial fuels are fuels used for the consumption in industrial machines. They include diesel fuel, black oil, kerosene and gasoline fuel etc. (Nelson, 1958)

Various types of industrial fuel exist, some of which include diesel containing 84.4% of carbon, 11.7% of hydrogen, 1.4% of nitrogen and 0.60% of sulphur, a boiling point of about 550⁰F (287.78⁰C), of 250⁰F (121.11⁰C) and its fractionated pouring temperature of 515⁰F (268.33⁰C). (Lowson, 1970)

It is used in heavy vehicle such as trucks and buses, and is becoming increasingly popular in cars and vans as light diesel engine technology develops. They are used in factories and building, for stationary equipment such as generator, furnace and small boilers. (Timasher, Sakhara *et al* 1989)

Black oil is another type of industrial fuel obtained from waste products collected after the major refining has taken place. Black oil has a boiling point of about 780⁰F (415.56⁰C), flash point of 400⁰F (204.44⁰C), dark brown in color and not as finely processed as light oil. They are widely used and sought after for ship propulsion, steam generator and power plants. (Lowson, 1970)

Kerosene is one of the refined products gotten from crude oil. It has the following chemical analysis 85.6% carbon, 12.4% of hydrogen and 0.37% of sulphur. Kerosene has a boiling point of about 335⁰F (168.33⁰C), its vapor pressure is 211⁰F (99.44⁰C) while the flash point of 110⁰F (43.33⁰C) and its fractionated pouring temperature of 305⁰F (151.67⁰C). It is the lightest, most volatile of the distillate fuel grades. It also has the following properties; Appearance-Clear and Bright; Colour (Saybolt), (min) + 20; Specific gravity at 15⁰C is 0.800 – 0.825 kg/m³

Petroleum (gasoline) is the major product in an industry of many by products. The chemical analysis of petroleum is 85.5% of carbon, 14.2% of hydrogen and some has 36% of oxygen. It has boiling points of about 80⁰F (26.67⁰C), its vapor pressure of about 20psi, and has fractionated pouring temperature of 60⁰F (15.56⁰C)

The flash point of a fuel is the lowest temperature at which vapor giving off will ignite when an external flame is applied under standard condition. The oil is said to be “flashed” appears and instantaneously, propagates itself over the center surface. The oil flashes because a flammable mixture results when it is heated sufficiently causing vapor to emerge and mix with oxygen in the air. (Nelson, 1958)

The flash point is defined to minimize fire risk during storage and handling the minimum flash point, for the machinery space of a merchant ship is govern by the International Legislation and the value is 60⁰C for fuels use for emergency purposes external to the machinery space, the flash must be greater than 43⁰C. The normal maximum storage temperature of a fuel is 10⁰C below the flash point, unless arrangements are otherwise made. (Nelson, 1958)

Some of the other properties required of a good fuel are Density which is the absolute relationship between mass and volume at a stated temperature. The S.I unit is kg/m³ at a reference temperature 15⁰C. (Clair, 1979); Viscosity which is a property of the internal resistance of a fluid that opposes the motion of adjacent layers. The unit of measure of the resistance in S.I unit is Pascal; Pour point which is the lowest temperature at which a fuel can be handled without excessive amount of wax crystal forming out of solution. If a fuel is below the pour points, wax will begin to separate out and this will block filter; it's carbon residue which is the tendency to form carbon deposited under high temperature conditions in an inert atmosphere. For straight run fuels, the typical value of carbon residue is between 10-12%mm, while for fuel derived from secondary conversion processing the value depends upon the severity of the process applied. On a global basis, this is typically 15-16%mm but in some areas can be as high as 20%MN/M. (Clair, 1979); Sulphur content which is a natural occurring element in the crude oil and concentrate in the residual component of the crude oil distillation process. Hence, the amount of sulphur in the fuel oil depends mainly on the source of the crude oil due to a lesser extension on the refining process. Typically for residual fuel on a world-wide basis, the value is in the order of 2-4% m/m.

Sediment

By extraction can be defined as the insoluble residues remaining after extraction by toluene. These insoluble residues are contaminants such as sands, dirt and resist scales that are not derived from the fuel. Such definition and test method are suitable for clear distillate fuels but are not applicable to residual fuels which are of greater importance to the total sediment contents of the fuel including hydrocarbon material which relates to stability. Stability or residual fuel may be defined as the ability of fuel to remain in unchanged condition despites circumstances which may tend to cause change or more simply as the resistance of oil to breakdown. Conversely, instability would be the tendency of a residual fuel to produce a deposit of asphaltenic sludge as a function of time or temperature.

In 1980s, three sediments test method were developed, where each relates to various aspects of the sediments. They are the total sediment extent (TSE), total sediment accelerate (TSA) and total sediment potential (TSP) methods. Each of the method is of filtration through a double filter paper and each differs in the treatment of the fuel sample prior to filtration. In the case of the TSE procedure, there is specific sample preparation and the sediment result relates to the dirt in the sample.

For TSA procedure, the sample is mixed with 10% ce-tane $-C_{16}H_{34}$ (a colorless oily hydrocarbon) and is being heated for 1 hour at $100^{\circ}C$ before filtration. In the case of TSP test the sample is heated for 24hours at $100^{\circ}C$ to stimulate thermal ageing of the fuel. In the event of lack of stability of a fuel it is likely that, filter blockage and combustion problems will be experienced. If there is any difficulty in identifying the nature of these materials, a small portion should be placed in an open container and be allowed to float in a vessel containing water at a temperature of 60 to $70^{\circ}C$. Many materials will therefore melts but an asphaltenic sludge will not (fig 1)

Fig1: Sediments test method of fuel samples by filtration

Compatibility

Every fuel is manufactured to be stable within tendency itself, with this, it does not have the tendency of producing asphaltenic sludge and it does not necessarily follow that two stable fuels are compatible when blended or mixed together while incompatible is the tendency of a residual fuel to produce a deposit on dilution or on blending with other fuel oils.

Problems of incompatibility within fuels are more but when they happen, there results are severe. Typical problems are sludging and blockage of bunker and service tank pipe runs, filters and centrifuge bowls. In extreme circumstances, the only remedy is the manual removal of the sludge build up. It is impossible to give precise advice on probability of compatibility problems between two fuels but the risk of incompatibility can be ranked. A blend is regarded as being stable if it is homogenous immediately after preparation. The remains in normal storage, at no time produce or tend to produce sludge on a significant scale. Under these circumstances, the fuels that form the blend are being considered as compatible with each other.

By definition, residual fuels are the remains of the crude oil after the more valuable component have been extracted from the manufacture of petroleum product. The chemical composition of residual fuels is difficult to define as it depends upon the source of the crude oil and the manufacturing process used in the extraction of the petroleum products.

However, when considering the chief constituent of residual fuel an appreciation that can be made on the sludge forming mechanism. These constituents of a residual fuel include asphalt, resins and liquid hydrocarbon. The generic terms 'asphaltenes' covers a wide range of heavier hydrocarbon structures. Besides, having high molecular weight and high hydrocarbon ratios, they may also contain small amount of other elements, depending on the source of the crude oil.

Asphaltenes are delivered to exist in residual fuel as 'micelles'. The resins can be considered as low molecular weight asphaltenes and these resins produce time solutions (i.e. molecular dispersion).

The resin molecules in an oil medium of residual fuel are known as 'maltanes' while the liquid hydrocarbons are in oily weight than the resins, which acts as a solvent for the other constituents. Thus a residual fuel oil is generally considered to contain a disperse phase of asphaltenes complex with high molecular weight component of the maltenes (resins) and liquid hydrocarbon in the form of a micelle. The continuous of intermicellar phase consist of ion molecular weight constituent of the maltenes.

In this ways one can visualize a general decrease in carbon/hydrogen ratio and molecular weight from the center of the micelle through to the continuous phase. This is shown diagrammatically in the figure; although, the hypothetical zones are shown separately. Although, they merge with each other so there is no distinct interphase between the micelle and intermicellar phase.

In conditions shown, equivalent exists and the 'micelles' are considered to be 'peptized' (i.e. colloidal dispersed). If, however, the carbon/hydrogen ratio of the Maltene is lowered, say by the introduction of a paraffin diluents, the resin which are absorbed in the asphaltenes are to a certain extent, absorb. This result in the asphalt particles got is being completely surrounded by resins and they are mutually attracted. This leads to a precipitation which appears as sludge.

	Fuel A	Fuel B
High risk	low density	density
Moderate risk	high risk	high density
Lowest risk	low density	high density

The profit margins of fuel delivery are often very small and it is tempting to improve this by water addition that is often difficult to dictate in a visual examination. Reputable suppliers will deliver fuel with water content far below ISO-8217 maximum limits.

In practice, the nature of the actual water present may be fresh, blackish or salty depending on the level of sodium as determined by the elementary analysis. On a worldwide basis the salt content of sea water varies but usually in first other terms 100mg/kg of sodium is associated with 1% of sea water. Grass water contamination will be removed by the centrifuge. (Sauvain, 1987)

Specific Energy

The specific energy of a fuel expressed in mg/kg depends on the composition. For residual fuel, the main constituent are carbon and hydrogen both of which releases energy on combustion. Sulphur also releases energy on combustion but to a lesser extent than carbon and hydrogen. The fuel density is mainly proportional to the ratio of carbon and hydrogen atoms in the fuels

Ignition Quality

The ignition quality of a fuel is a measure of the relative ease by which it will ignite. For distillate fuels this is measured by ce-tane number. Ce-tane number is determined by testing in a special engine with a variable compression ratio. The higher the number the more easily the fuel will ignite in the engine. For residual fuel, there are two accepted empirical equation both based on the density and viscosity of the fuel. They are calculated carbon aromaticity index (CCAI) and calculated ignition index (CII) The CCAI gives members in the range of 800 – 870, while the CII gives values in that same order as a ce-tane index for distillate fuels of the two equations CCAI values are more frequently quoted.

The figure is monogram, which incorporates both CII and CCAI. If the viscosity is fixed and the density is raised the CII value falls and the CCAI value increases. Similarly, the density is fixed and the viscosity is lowered, the CII value falls and the CCAI value is increased, in general values less than 30. For CII and greater than 870, for CCAI are considered problematic if required, further guidance on acceptable on acceptable quality value should be obtained from the engine manufacturer. (Clair, 1979)

Ash - The ash value is related to the inorganic materials in the fuel oil. The actual value depends upon three factors, firstly the inorganic materials naturally present in the crude oil, secondly the refinery process employed. (Sauvain, 1987)

Factors affecting fuel-oil combustion

Combustion of fuel

This is the amount of heat liberated when a unit quantity of a fuel is burned. It is termed heating value or heat of combustion. This is simply the burning of fuel oil through the mixture of oil and air in the combustion chamber with the right atomizing power to produce the necessary firing.

Factors Affecting Fuel and Combustion

There are various properties of fuel oil that has effect on it's combustion. Its presence are endlessly in the fuel oil. They are contained as fuel oil element.

Sulphur

This is a naturally-occurring element in crude oil. The level of sulphur has a marginal effect on specific energy on combustion process. In diesel engine, its presence in the fuel can potentially give rise to corrosive wear which can minimize the rate of combustion. (Lowson, 1970)

Water and Sediment

The presence of high level of water contamination in the oil is known to be actually risen to the flash point. Water contaminations can also give a false low flash, particularly in certain mini-flash systems that use change in pressure to detect flash. The boiling off of the water can give a false positive on fuel for instance this can also snuff out the flame in cases when a gas pilot is used.

Sediment

These are deposits, which exist on insoluble residues. They are contaminant such as sands, dirt and rust scale which give rise to incomplete combustion of fuel in the combustion chamber of the furnace burner.

Vanadium and Sodium - Vanadium is a metal that is present in all crude oil in an oil-insoluble form. Vanadium and sodium in combination are high levels which can results in high temperature corrosion damage to valve and turbo changer components.

Aluminum and Silicon - These are generally accepted that an indication of Aluminum represents the potential presence of catalyst fines. These fines are particles of spent catalyst arising from the catalytic cracking process in the refinery. These fines are in the form of complex Alumino-silicates. If not reduced by the suitable fuel treatment, the abrasive nature of the fines does damage the engine oil particularly the fuel pumps, injectors, pistons, rings and liners.

METHODOLOGY

This experiment was carried out in Ramat Polytechnic and University of Maiduguri at the end of the year 2007. The equipments employed to carry out the work include crucible furnace, fuel tank , inlet pipe, wire gauze, flexible hose, the injector nozzles, the electric motor blower, the delivery hose, the control knob, the mixture chamber, the combustion chamber, the crucible furnace and the crucible pots (the excavators). The experiment was tested first with diesel and then with the used engine oil so as to compare their efficiency and economic viability.

Four liters of industrial fuel (diesel) was poured into the tank and the valve was tightly locked (air and fuel). Ten kilograms of zinc scraps was placed inside the crucible pot and placed inside the furnace. The furnace was lit by pouring some quantity of paper into the furnace and ignited.

As the paper was burning the control valve of the fuel and the air control valve was opened; the blower control switch was switched on for the combustion to take place. The starting time for the firing was noted, the control points of the valve was also noted and marked for further control levels. The fuel was allowed to burn off and the final reading of the time was taken. The valves were locked and the electric blower was switched off. The melted scrap inside the crucible pot was emptied into a container. The same procedure was adopted using used engine oil and kerosene. Various ratio of the used engine oil to kerosene was tested.

The mixture should be thoroughly mixed to avoid dense fuel burning first (used engine oil) while the kerosene settles and burn last. The mixture is also filtered very well to avoid particles of stones, sand, metal chips, wood e.t.c passing into the system which will block the injector nozzles

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiment conducted was used to determine the correct proportion of mixture of used engine oil with kerosene that will help achieve optimum result in foundry application. The results were obtained relative to the rate of burning and the intensity of the firing.

The ratios used for the experiment and the times taken to melt 10kg of zinc were as shown in table 1

Table 1 Determination of appropriate combination of mixture

Proportion	Time (minutes)	Qty (liter)
6:1	22	4
5:1	21	4
4:1	19	4
3:1	17	4
5:2	16	4
5:3	17	4
3:2	17	4
2:1	16	4

Fig. 2: Testing of different types of fuel samples

The result showed that with higher percentage of kerosene in the mixture, the intensity of burning is very high. This may not be good for casting that requires gradual melting. As the quantity of the used engine oil increases while the kerosene decreases, the intensity of burning gradually decrease while the time of melting increase (Fig 2). At a ratio of 6:1 of used engine oil and kerosene, gradual and effective

melting occurs even though the time required to melt the material; in this case zinc, increases. Figure 3 shows this gradual but effective melting of sample in relation to proportion of mixtures.

Even though used engine oil has a high flash point, its rate of burning is low. This can be attributed the presence of impurities inside.

Fig. 4.2 Proportion of mixture in relation to time of melting

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

From the experiment carried out, it has being observed that kerosene and used engine oil can be used in foundry workshop for firing crucible furnace effectively. For economy in large scale operation, the admixture of used engine oil blended with kerosene at a ratio of 6:1 can be an alternative to these industrial fuels when the used engine oil has been properly treated. That is, removal of un-wanted sediments that may be harmful to castings e.g. sulphur. This kind of foundry workshop can be utilized for the purpose of teaching/training student in our various institution of learning and can help to save cost of running foundry workshop.

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